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Research Article

A Study of Knowledge Assessment by Using Various Variables in PCOD Patients

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) is the most common endocrine disorder in women aged 18-44 years. It usually starts during adolescence, but symptoms may fluctuate over time. PCOS can cause hormonal imbalances, irregular periods, excess androgen levels and cysts in the ovary. **Methods:** Prospective study was conducted in patients with PCOD disease. They were randomly approached by sending them the questionnaire form to Area hospital in Narsaraopet, palnadu. **Tool:** A structured multiple-choice questionnaire, including demographic variables and knowledge assessment on PCOS, was used for data collection. **Results:** This study includes 47 patients among that the no. of patients are affected with the age group of >19 years. The PCOD is mainly caused by eating junk food. The PCOD patients have their menstruating days of 4-5 days. **Conclusion:** The data will be collected and analysed from the questionnaire form and patient data.

INTRODUCTION

Polycystic ovary syndrome is a common hormonal condition that affects women of reproductive age. It usually starts during adolescence, but symptoms may fluctuate over time. PCOS can cause hormonal imbalances, irregular periods, excess androgen levels and cysts in the ovaries¹.

Causes-

Pelvic inflammatory disease: Pelvic inflammatory disease (PID) is a group of upper genital tract

infections that involves endometritis, salpingitis, tubo ovarian blisters, and/or pelvic peritonitis (Workowski and Berman, 2010². **Endometriosis:** Endometriosis can be defined as the occurrence of endometrial glands and stroma like wounds external to the uterus (Giudice and Kao, 2004). The wounds may be peritoneal wounds, superficial embeds or cysts on the ovary, or deep penetrating disease (Nisolle and Donnez, 1997). Endometriosis is mainly found in young women;

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however its incidence is not linked with racial or societal group discrepancies. Uterine **fibriods:** Uterine fibriods is the abnormal cells formed in the tissues of uterus. Uterine fibroids are benign smooth muscle neoplasms of the uterus that cause disturbances in women of reproductive age. The most usual exhibiting symptom is heavy menstrual bleeding, which may be directed to anaemia, and fatigue and sore periods (Stewart, 2001)³. Uterine adenomyosis: Uterine adenomyosis is a pathological condition portrayed by the manifestation of endometrial glands and stroma inside the myometrium (Abha et al., 2012) that means the lines of uterus grows into the muscle of uterus. It is mostly accepted that adenomyosis appears as soon as the normal border-line between the endometrial basal layer and the myometrium get disjointed. Uterine anomalies: Uterine anomalies are a spectrum of congenital uterine anatomic abnormalities derived from defect in the growth of mullerian ducts in fetal development (Javain and Ahmadi, 2015). These are accompanied with higher incidences of infertility, repeated abortions, intrauterine fetal death, intrauterine growth retardation, untimely delivery, fetal malposition, caesarean section, retained placenta (Ahmadi and Haghghi, 2012; Moini et al., 2013) and gynecological difficulties such as hematocolpos and hematometra⁴. Endometrial polyps: Endometrial polyps are excessive growth in glands, blood vessels, and stroma inside the uterine cavity and are usually benign (Fleischer et al., 2011). They mainly derive from the fundal region and spread to the internal and can be observed single or multiple. Endometrial hyperplasia: Endometrial hyperplasia is described as an anomalous production of endometrial glands of different size and shape, which causes thickened endometrium (Davis et al., 2002). It arises after the continuous excess estrogen stimulation of any source (Hannemann et al., 2010). Polycystic ovarian syndrome patients are usually expected to

have hyperplasia because of higher circulating estrogen levels. Premature ovarian failure: Premature ovarian failure or insufficiency (POF) is a condition represented by amenorrhoea, decreased estrogen and elevated gonadotropin levels in women aged < 40 years. POF is the consequence of untimely exhaustion of the follicular pool, or can be ascribed to follicular dysfunction. Anti-Mullerian hormone (AMH), a growth factor secreted entirely by small, maturing follicles in the ovary, can be considered as an indicator which calculates whether women are at risk of POF since serum levels of this hormone intensely associated with the number of growing follicles⁵

Ovarian cyst: Ovarian cyst is a usual gynaecological problem and is classified into two major types; physiological and pathological (Grimes et al., 2014). Physiological cysts are follicular cysts and luteal cysts. Pathological cysts are regarded as ovarian tumors, which may be benign, malignant and marginal. Benign tumors are very frequent in youthful females, but malignant are more common in aged females (Hongqian et al., 2013). The indications and symptoms of ovarian cysts may encompass pelvic pain, dysmenorrheal, and dyspareunia. Further signs comprise biliousness, vomiting, or breast soreness, fullness and weightiness in the abdomen and frequency and difficulty in releasing of the bladder (Farghaly, 2014)⁶.

Aim: A study of the study of knowledge assessment by using various variables in PCOD patients.

Objectives:

1. To identify PCOD patients with different age groups.
2. To collect the demographic variables by using data collection form.
3. To assess the knowledge of PCOD patients by using questionnaire form.

1. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study design:

The study was conducted at Area hospital, palnadu road, Narsaraopet in 6 months of period.

Study method:

Patient details were obtained from patient case sheet and required data entered in data collection

form. The data collected based on various parameters like Age, Weight, Height, Body mass index, Eating habits, Family income, Mother education, consuming junk food, No. of mensruating days, Menstrual cycle.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Sl. no	Demographical variables	No. of patients	Percentage
1	Age		
	a) Below 19 years	5	10.63%
	b) 19 years	24	51.06%
	c) 20 years	14	29.78%
	d) Above 21 years	4	8.53%
2	Weight		
	a) Below 45kg	4	8.52
	b) 45 to 50 kg	23	48.93
	c) 50 to 59 kg	17	36.17
	d) Above 60 kg	3	6.38
3	Height		
	a) Below 140 cm	5	10.63%
	b) 140 to 145 cm	22	46.81%
	c) 145 to 150 cm	18	38.30%
	d) Above 150 cm	2	4.26%
4	BMI		
	a) 18 to 21	3	6.38%
	b) 22 to 25	24	51.06%
	c) 26 to 29	18	38.29%
	d) Above 30	2	4.27%
5	Eating habits		
	a) Street food	24	51.06%
	b) Homemade food	17	36.17%
	c) Organic food	4	8.51%
	d) As per availability	2	4.26%
6	Menstrual cycle		
	a) Irregular	21	44.68%
	b) 20 to 25 days	8	17.02%
	c) 25 to 30 days	9	19.15%
	d) 30 to 35 days	9	19.15%
7	Family income		
	a) Less than 10,000 per month	17	36.17%
	b) 10,000to 30,000per month	18 12	38.29% 25.54%

	c) Greater than 30,000per month		
8	Mother's education a) Literate b) Illiterate	39 8	82.97% 17.03%
9	Do you consume junk food a) Yes b) No	42 5	89.36% 10.64%
10	Source of information a) Health personnel b) Parent c) Mass media d) Text book e) No information	23 5 13 0 6	48.96% 10.68% 27.66% 0% 12.7%
11	Menarche a) 10 to 12 years b) 12 to 14 years c) 14 to 16 years d) Below 10 years	5 27 15 0	10.63% 57.44% 31.93% 0
12	Number of Menstruating days a) 4 to 5 days b) Less than 4 days c) More than 5 days	29 13 5	61.70% 27.66% 10.64%
13.	Does anyone in family have PCOS a) Yes b) No	40 7	85.10% 14.89%
14.	Experience of menstrual cramps a) Yes b) No	40 7	85.10 14.89%
15	Relieving the pain a) Take pain killers b) Use heat compressions c) Use ayurvedic supplements d) None of the above	13 23 6 5	27.66% 48.98% 12.76% 10.66%

The present study included 47 patients. Based on age group the patients having 19 years are more prone to PCOD. Based on weight, the PCOD

patients are 45-50 kgs. Based on BMI the more no. of patients having 22-25 of BMI. Based on eating habits, the more no. of patients are eating

junk food than homely food. Based on menstrual cycle, the patients are having irregular periods. Based on menarche, the PCOD patients are having menarche at the age of 12-14 years. Based on no. of menstruating days the PCOD patients having 4-5 days of menstruating days. Among 47 patients the more no. of patients experiencing the menstrual cramps. The more no. of patients using heat compressions for relieving the pain.

2. CONCLUSION:

The data will be collected and analyzed from the questionnaire form and patient data .

The data plays a major role in the results.

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REFERENCES

1. Balen, A. (2001). Polycystic ovary syndrome and cancer. *Human reproduction update*, 7(6), 522-52.
2. Bermen., Conway, G. S., Kaltsas, G., Techatrasak, K., Manning, P. J., West, C., & Jacobs, S. (1995). Andrology: Polycystic ovary syndrome: the spectrum of the disorder in 1741 patients. *Human Reproduction*, 10(8), 2107-2111.
3. Stevart, Barry, J. A., Azizia, M. M., & Hardiman, P. J. (2014). Risk of endometrial, ovarian and breast cancer in women with polycystic ovary syndrome: a systematic review and meta analysis. *Human Reproduction Update*, 20(5), 748-758.
4. Moini. et. al, Brinton, L. A., Moghissi, K. S., Westhoff, C. L., Lamb, E. J., & Scoccia, B. (2010). Cancer risk among infertile women with androgen excess or menstrual disorders (including polycystic ovary syndrome). *Fertility and Sterility*, 94(5), 1787-1792.

5. Butenas, S., Orfeo, T., & Mann, K. G. (2008). Tissue factor activity and function in blood coagulation. *Thrombosis Research*, 122, S42-S46.
6. Farghaly, Dunaif, A., Xia, J., Book, C. B., Schenker, E., & Tang, Z. (1995). Excessive insulin receptor serine phosphorylation in cultured fibroblasts and in skeletal muscle. A potential mechanism for insulin resistance in the polycystic ovary syndrome. *The Journal of clinical investigation*, 96(2), 801-810.

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